

A Spy Among Partners: An Analysis Of How Chinese Data Harvesting Threatens Brazil's Sovereignty

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Abstract

The central point is to understand that autonomy and influence are indispensable concepts in the debate on digital sovereignty. Even among partner countries, transferring data through fragile regulatory frameworks constitutes an irresponsible long-term strategy, given the immense power embedded in this asset. The paradox becomes even more evident when one observes that many of these countries, while benefiting from the massive collection of data originating from societies with weaker institutional protection, simultaneously establish robust regulatory barriers within their own jurisdictions to safeguard their citizens and informational infrastructures. In this sense, while their domestic legislation imposes strict limits on the circulation and exploitation of national data, information originating from emerging countries (as frequently occurs with Brazil) becomes abundant raw material for the training, experimentation, and refinement of these technologies. Within this scenario of gradual disempowerment, data extraction becomes a form of power. Relinquishing such an asset (even to partner countries) constitutes a dangerous strategy in the long run. It is therefore necessary to pursue alternative paths that strengthen Brazil's sovereignty, rather than merely replacing one form of Western dependence with another.

Keywords: Brazil; Autonomy; Data; China.

Introduction

As argued by the journalist Andy Lewis, it is evident that in times of technological innovation, the rule is clear: when you don't see the product, you are the one being marketed. In this sense, it is important to understand that although military power and human capital still have a lot of power in global movements, data has consolidated as the most powerful asset a country could have, with its massive collection being a powerful enabler to optimize supply chains, understand the market, influence various sectors and even strengthen (or not) the security of countries, it all depends on which side the nation is on: those who collect data, or those who are dependent and deliver the most valuable item they possess.

To understand what this article intends to address, it is first necessary to know a term and differentiate some expressions that translate this tension in times of digital surveillance. At first, it is normal for the popular imagination, thanks to cinematographic fictions, to think that AIs will dominate the world in an almost supernatural way, however, this is already happening, but in a much more subtle and voluntary way than one might think. The term "gradual disempowerment" (Kulveit et al., 2025) captures a gradual loss of human control over AIs, due to something that citizens themselves do: they are seduced by the growing capabilities of artificial intelligence and voluntarily cede their human influence little by little, for example, by using mechanisms like ChatGPT in almost all social functions, work, decision making, artistic creation and even companionship. With this, massive data collection is carried out and the human race becomes more and more dependent on artificial intelligences for things that they could easily do.

Autonomy and Influence

With this established, it's time to go to the main distinction of this article, essential to understand the existing power system in the international field. As argued by Benjamin Cohen, "power must begin with autonomy, which generates a potential for leverage. Influence the deliberate activation of leverage, should then be thought of as functionally derivative" (Cohen, 2019a, p. 23). In other words, in the scenario discussed here, influence consists of the ability to affect and interfere in the life (or politics) of others, while autonomy is the starting point of everything, and one of the most essential things in international law: the ability to prevent the actions of others from affecting oneself. That means, articulated powers, like the USA, have as much influence as autonomy, while countries like Brazil do not fully possess either of them. Why is this important for the data harvesting theme? Because when we talk about data extraction and analysis, from the perspective of an emerging country like Brazil, we perceive a total lack of autonomy, since this procedure is carried out by third parties, however, when we go to China's perspective, for instance, we are talking not only about possession of influence and autonomy over its own territory, but also over countries like Brazil.

The Legal Field

Furthermore, it is important to highlight the differences between the Brazilian and Chinese normative models. While in Brazil one still observes, depending on the subject matter, the coexistence of several applicable law (even with the LGPD serving as the foundational legislation, which still presents aspects that require improvement for the effective guarantee of sovereignty). China enacted, in 2016, the Cybersecurity Law of the People's Republic of China, recently amended at the beginning of 2026. When contrasted with the Brazilian case, it becomes evident that the Chinese regulation established structural foundations for the security of network operations, data localization, and data protection. It is a piece of legislation characterized by a high degree of rigor, reinforcing state control over the flow of national data and granting broad powers to supervisory authorities to sanction those who violate the law, particularly foreign companies operating within the Chinese digital system.

Both in its original text and in its subsequent amendments, one can observe the construction of a normative framework in which cybersecurity and national security are understood as instruments of power, governance, sovereignty, and economic and geopolitical competition. When examining the Brazilian process, however, the same level of caution and regulatory rigor cannot be identified, due to factors that influenced the legislative process itself. Finally, the central dilemma cannot be ignored: China has structured a framework aimed at shielding its own data, yet it does not refrain from accessing the data of others, whereas Brazil has not adopted measures to protect its autonomy. In this context, Chinese interests would hardly be constrained by bonds of friendship, strategic partnerships, or moral considerations that might prevent the collection and processing of Brazilian data, a dynamic that is not limited to China, but is equally observable among powers such as the United States or the members of the European Union.

Conclusion

The central question concerns the position occupied by Brazil within the international system, situated amid the strategic disputes of major powers. Diplomatic relations and partnerships regarded as strategic cannot presume unrestricted trust between states. Information and data constitute instruments of power and control; therefore, depending on national interests and shifting geopolitical circumstances, even allied nations may employ them in ways that may ultimately prove harmful when analysed in a gradual disempowerment movement.

Within this context, Brazil's technological dependence increases its vulnerability to practices of digital surveillance conducted by other nations. At the same time, this reality does not allow for simplistic solutions. Brazil remains embedded in a global technological system from which it cannot immediately disengage, particularly given the country's limited domestic capacity for technological development and production. Moreover, regulation itself becomes

a point of fragility. The recent debate surrounding the regulation of digital platforms in Brazil illustrates this vulnerability, revealing that the Brazilian National Congress may also be subject to international pressures capable of influencing the legislative process, potentially resulting in weakened regulatory frameworks unable to adequately address the challenges posed to national sovereignty.

In a neutral analysis, without entering into moral judgments, the Chinese regulatory model may be regarded as commendable in its firm protection of national data and in sanctioning foreign companies that fail to comply with its legal framework. Nevertheless, the Great Firewall and the system of domestic surveillance significantly compromise the privacy of Chinese citizens due to the high concentration of control exercised by the state. For this reason, among others beyond the scope of this article, such a model would be largely inapplicable to the Brazilian context.

The purpose of this discussion is not to suggest that Brazil should replicate such an approach, but rather to emphasize that national autonomy is essential to prevent unchecked external influence within the global digital environment. Although Brazilian diplomacy is known for its cooperative and conciliatory character, it is necessary to recognize that other countries (including strategic partners) currently hold access to one of the nation's most valuable assets: data. In the long term, such access represents a significant and potentially dangerous source of power.

This concern becomes even more relevant given the persistent difficulty in reaching consensus among the countries of the BRICS bloc. Under these circumstances, Brazil risks overlooking alternative technological paths (such as locally developed AI models and community networks) that could contribute to greater digital autonomy. Consequently, the pursuit of digital independence may become a superficial discourse that merely replaces Western technological colonialism with new dynamics of monopoly, governmental authoritarianism, and corporate abuse, creating further obstacles to the effective consolidation of Brazilian sovereignty.

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